

THE FUNDAMENTALS OF COMPREHENSIVE DEVELOPMENT OF YOUTH THROUGH VOLLEYBALL

Naubetullaev Tileubay Tolibaevich

Teacher of the Nukus branch of the Uzbekistan State University of
Physical Education and Sports

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7960984>

Abstract. Volleyball is an effective means of comprehensive physical development, with the help of which the tasks of improving health and improving the efficiency of youth are implemented. Therefore, the article presents the investigation of the process of development of volleyball as a sport among youth in our country. The results of the research depicted that the youth are highly motivated in training with the sport: volleyball this is due to the fact that volleyball affect their health and work positively.

Keywords: sport, physical education, volleyball, factors, effects, development, Uzbekistan, healthy life style.

In our country, a number of regulatory and legal documents aimed at the development of the field of physical education have been adopted and are being rapidly implemented. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5924 of January 24, 2020 "On measures to further improve and popularize physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan" is among them [1]. In accordance with this decision, the concept of development of physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2025 was drawn up. This concept defines the goals, objectives and long-term development of the state policy in the field of physical education and sports, including:

- To improve the level of health of the country's population by 2025;
- to increase the total number of citizens, pupils and students who regularly engage in physical education and sports;
- to increase the weekly movement activity of the population by organizing various public sports events among the employees of state bodies, enterprises and organizations, and the population;
- step by step implementation of the organizational system and the process of training and selection of talented young athletes on the principle of "educational institutions - sports school - higher sports" in educating young people and ensuring their employment;
- introduction of other modern methods and directions in the field of sports;

Volleyball is one of the most popular and affordable mass sports. Playing volleyball does not require large financial costs and serious physical preparation. A ball, a suitable playground, and a few people willing to play are all we need to have a fun and healthy time. In the absence of a special volleyball court with a net, we can simply play standing in a circle, as is done in the summer on many beaches in our country [3].

Volleyball is characterized by a great variety of game situations, the need to quickly respond to them, numerous jumping movements, constant variability in the intensity of physical and emotional stress. All this has a positive effect on the human body and promotes health and longevity. At the same time, volleyball is a traumatic sport, so it is necessary to

warm up before starting the game, and the intensity and duration of the game should depend on the age, physical condition and individual characteristics of the person [6, 18].

There some benefits of volleyball for youth:

- Regular playing of volleyball has a hardening effect on the body, increases the body's endurance.
- Strengthens the cardiovascular system and improves blood circulation.
- Positive effect on the respiratory system.
- A variety of movements and a variable load intensity during volleyball exercises trains almost all muscle groups.
- Volleyball strengthens the musculoskeletal system, improves joint mobility [4].
- Trains the muscles of the eyes, expands the field of view.
- Volleyball has a positive effect on the nervous system, improves mood, helps fight stress and depression.
- Volleyball trains agility, movement accuracy, mobility and flexibility.
- Volleyball lessons develop in children and adults such qualities as hard work, courage, perseverance, discipline and the ability to quickly respond to changing situations.
- Help a person to overcome complexes, to be liberated, to find a common language with peers and people of different generations.
- Volleyball and other team sports instill a sense of responsibility towards the team, the ability to work in a team and trust others.

Volleyball is a fairly popular sport in our country. This trend is due to several factors, including: a high level of training of players, support from the state, a large number of tournaments and competitions [2, 35].

The main factors which affect to attract youth to play volleyball are the followings: [5]

First, emotions. The game itself is very emotional. Each goal scored or missed brings positive or negative emotions. But there is nothing better in this game than after a long and hard rally, to score the ball into the opponent's field. Volleyball players know these incomparable sensations that the game brings.

Second, team play. Volleyball is not a game that is built on the skill of one player. This game is the skill and coherence of all team members. They should feel each other, help out comrades and cheer them up. Without this, there will never be good results that the team is striving for. This is the most important moment in volleyball.

The team played will most often win the team, each member who is strong in individual skill, but playing with the rest of the team members for the first time.

Thirdly, physical development. Volleyball develops reaction and communication, keeps fit, improves coordination, helps to forget the problems that have arisen in life. By playing it, you can find a huge number of great friends and people with whom you can continue to communicate in the future.

Fourth- no special conditions and physical form of the player are needed. You can play volleyball anywhere and it does not require any special training. You need to have only one thing - desire.

Fifth, motivation. There are certain goals in volleyball: victory, team play, etc. And this person is driven to develop more and more physically and spiritually.

Sixth, responsibility. Volleyball is a team game, and the mistake of one player usually brings the whole team down.

Seventh, concentration. After a series of losses, it is very important to get together psychologically and continue to play, because the game is not over yet.

If youth play volleyball regularly, they will have the following positive results:

- After each game, mentally look at your game from the outside, analyze the mistakes, correct them in training and try not to make them in the future. The game of volleyball must always fight to the end and believe that everything will work out in the end. After all, today we will reap the fruits that we sowed yesterday

This sport develops the following qualities in teenagers:

- Ability to communicate with peers. Through team play, children learn to interact with each other to achieve a common goal;
- Diligence. Adolescents involved in sports begin to realize the value of their work, and strive in everything and always to achieve the best results;
- Self-confidence. Teamwork allows you to develop self-confidence and the desire to show your best side. Team support has a positive effect on social adaptation, and in the future, a teenager will boldly go towards adult goals.

Conclusion. Taking all into account it can be stated that In addition, volleyball has a positive effect on the physical and intellectual development of a teenager. Children involved in the sections show the best results in their studies and are distinguished by endurance and strong immunity. For general physical development, the type of volleyball does not matter. One can send a teenager to the school section or beach volleyball, the benefits of this will be invaluable in any case.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining Farmoni, 24.01.2020 yildagi PF-5924-son
2. Pulatov A.A., Isroilov Sh.X., Qurbonova M.A., Kodirova M.A. I-IV kurs talabalari bilan seminar va uslubiy mashg'ulotlar o'tkazish bo'yicha uslubiy ishlanmalar (voleybol nazariyasi va uslubiyati bo'yicha). T.: 2008. – 78b.

3. Qo'chqarova O.V., Qirchoqov V.V., Boltayev G.V. Voleybol. o'quv qo'llanma. 2001y. Toshkent

4. Айрапетьянц Л.Р. Волейбол. Учебник. 2000 г. Ташкент.

5. Хулио Веласко (Аргентина), Даг Бил (США), Филип Блен (Франция), Джузеппе Азарра (Италия). Современный волейбол. //Тренировка. Управление. Тенденции. – М.: “ВФВ”, 2008. – 31с.

6. Шнайдер В.Ю. Методика обучения игре в волейбол. // Пособие для ст-в фак-в физ-ры. – М.: “Олимпия”, 2008. – 55 с.

